

STUDIES IN THE PYRIDINE SERIES. PART IV. SYNTHESSES OF SOME BASES OF THE PYRIDINE GROUP*

BY RAFAT HUSAIN SIDDIQUI, R. H. USMANI AND SYED MAQSUD ALI

Diethyl 2 : 6-dimethyl-4-propyl-1 : 4-dihydropyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate has been obtained by condensing ethyl-acetoacetate, butyric aldehyde and ammonia in presence of piperidine. The dihydro ester on oxidation in alcohol with nitrous fumes gives 2 : 6-dimethyl-4-propylpyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate. The potassium salt of this when distilled with soda-lime gives 2 : 6-dimethyl-4-propylpyridine, which when condensed with benzaldehyde in presence of acetic anhydride, gives 2-styryl-4-propyl-6-methylpyridine and 2 : 6-distyryl-4-propylpyridine. All the bases give well-defined crystalline salts

The object of this series of investigation is to place on record syntheses of the bases of the pyridine group and to correlate alkyl groups with reference to their positions with toxicity. The latter object has not yet been achieved. The synthesis has been effected by Hantzsch's general method for pyridines as modified by Siddiqui (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 410, 415). Ethylacetoacetate, butyric aldehyde and ammonia condense together in presence of piperidine to yield diethyl 2 : 6-dimethyl-4-propyl-1 : 4-dihydropyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate, m.p. 125° and this gives diethyl 2 : 6-dimethyl-4-propylpyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate on oxidation with nitrous acid in alcoholic solution. The crude potassium salt obtained by hydrolysis of the ester with alcoholic potassium hydroxide after distillation with soda-lime gives 2 : 6-dimethyl-4-propylpyridine, b. p. 193-95° and yields well-defined salts. The tri-alkyl base is condensed with benzaldehyde in presence of acetic anhydride to yield 2-styryl-4-propyl-6-methylpyridine, 2 : 6-distyryl-4-propylpyridine and some unreacted base. The three bases have been separated *via* their salts (*vide* experimental). The distyryl base does not condense with benzaldehyde further and the gold complex of the base shows abnormal behaviour. The methiodides of the bases are not obtained by keeping the reactants in chloroform solution at room temperature and to obtain them in quantitative yield it is necessary to heat the solution under pressure at 100°. The monostyryl derivative on oxidation gives benzoic acid and 2-methyl-4-propylpyridine-6-carboxylic acid. The carboxylic acid, m.p. 60° forms copper (m.p. 185-87°), ammonium and silver (m.p. 222°, decomp.) salts. The acid on decarboxylation with a trace of copper powder gives 2-methyl-4-propylpyridine which has been characterised by the picrate, m.p. 117°.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Butyric Aldehyde.—n-Butyl alcohol (b. p. 116·8°, 300 c.c., 1·6 mol.) was oxidised by gradually adding a solution of potassium dichromate (414 g, 0·56 mol.), sulphuric acid (296 c.c., 2 mols.) in water (1420 c.c.). From the distillate on drying over sodium sulphate a fraction distilling at 70-75° was collected, yield 66 g., b. p. 73-74° (Brühl, *Annalen*, 1880, 203, 18).

Diethyl 2 : 6-Dimethyl-4-propyl-1 : 4-dihydropyridine-3 : 5-dicarboxylate.—A mixture of ice-cold ethyl acetoacetate (195 g., 2 mols), butyric aldehyde (54 g., 1 mol.) and piperidine (6g.) was kept at 0° for 2 hours. Dry ammonia gas (a little more than 1 mol., 13·2 g.) was passed into the mixture at 0° which then was heated in a closed flask at 100° for 4 hours. After cooling the light yellow condensate was decomposed with water when bright yellow dihydro-ester was obtained as needles (yield 165 g., 75%) After crystallisation from ethanol as pale yellow prisms it had m.p. 125°. The ester is soluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, chloro-

* A note on an isomer of dimethylethylpyridine (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **18**, 505) may be considered as Part III of this series

form, ether and ethyl acetate. (Found in material dried at 100° : C, 65.4; H, 8.5; N, 5.1. $C_{16}H_{22}O_4N$ requires C, 65.1; H, 8.5; N, 4.7 per cent).

The foregoing dihydro-ester in alcoholic suspension was oxidised with nitrous fumes till the ester dissolved in the solvent and a drop of the solution gave no turbidity with hydrochloric acid. The acid solution after making alkaline with sodium carbonate was shaken with ether. The ether solution was washed with water and dried over potassium hydroxide. The solvent was removed and the residue was extracted with petroleum ether in which the original dihydro-ester was insoluble. The unchanged ester was reoxidised. The solvent was removed and the pale yellow oily base distilled at 210° to a colourless liquid having a deep pyridine like smell (yield 60 g.). The *picrate* of the base was obtained as lemon-yellow needles from ethyl alcohol, m.p. $90-91^{\circ}$.

The foregoing base (60 g.) was hydrolysed with 20% alcoholic potassium hydroxide (500 c.c.) by refluxing over sand-bath for 8 hours when potassium salt separated. This as well as the residue obtained by removal of the solvent (1 part) was intimately mixed with soda lime (2 parts). The mixture after drying at 100° was distilled and the distillate was taken up in ether, the ethereal solution after washing with water was dried over potassium hydroxide. After removal of the solvent an oily base was obtained.

2 : 6-Dimethyl-4-propylpyridine distilled at $193-95^{\circ}$ and is soluble in common organic solvents, yield 9.7 g.

The *hydrochloride* was obtained as yellow needles by passing hydrogen chloride into the ethereal solution of the base. It is soluble in chloroform, acetone and water.

The *picrate* of the base was obtained as bright yellow prisms, m.p. 83° and is soluble in chloroform, alcohol, acetone, methanol, ethyl acetate and benzene but insoluble in ether and petroleum ether. [Found in anhydrous material: C, 51.1; H, 5.1; N, 14.8. $C_{16}H_{18}N \cdot C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 50.8; H, 4.8; N, 14.8 per cent].

The *aurichloride* was obtained as bright yellow needles by adding 5% solution of gold chloride to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride. It softens at 137° and gradually melts at 145° and is soluble in methanol, acetone and ethyl acetate. (Found in material dried at 100° : Au, 40.35. $C_{16}H_{18}N \cdot HCl \cdot AuCl_3$ requires Au, 40.22 per cent).

The *chloroplatinate* separated as dull orange coloured precipitate on adding 5% platinum chloride solution to an aqueous solution of the hydrochloride. It crystallised from alcohol as bright orange prismatic needles, m.p. 220° and is soluble in ethanol and methanol and insoluble in chloroform and acetone. [Found in substance dried at 100° : Pt, 27.36. $(C_{16}H_{18}N \cdot HCl)_2 \cdot PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 27.48 per cent].

The *Methiodide*.—A solution of the base (0.5 g., 1 mol.) in chloroform and methyl iodide (0.5 g., 1.2 mol.) was left well corked overnight but no methiodide separated. This solution was therefore heated in a sealed tube at 100° for 7 hours when it turned red. On adding ether the methiodide separated quantitatively in large colourless needles, m.p. 182° . It is soluble in chloroform, acetone, ethanol and water.

Condensation of 2 : 6-Dimethyl-4-propylpyridine with Benzaldehyde.—A mixture of the base (8 g., 1 mol.), freshly distilled benzaldehyde (11.4 g., 2 mols.) and acetic anhydride (11 g., 2 mols.) was gently refluxed for 14 hours. The dark coloured condensate was acidified with 10% hydrochloric acid and distilled in steam to remove benzaldehyde. The residue was dissolved in hydrochloric acid when a clear solution (A) was obtained leaving behind a dark pasty mass. This was successively extracted with 25%, 40% and 60% glacial acetic acid and the solutions on treatment with 50% hydrochloric acid yielded identical yellow precipitates

(B) which were purified from the tarry impurities by washing with ether. The filtrate from (B) after washing with ether was mixed with (A). Nothing could be obtained from the tarry impurities contained in ether solution.

The clear yellow solution (A) was made alkaline with an aqueous solution of sodium carbonate and shaken with ether. The ether solution was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and after removal of the solvent gave a light brown oily mixture of bases. The unreacted base (2 : 6-dimethyl-4-propylpyridine) distilling up to 200°, was removed and identified by conversion to the picrate, m.p. 83°. The residue distilled at 240°/740 mm. to a thick oily liquid and proved to be 2-styryl-4-propyl-6-methylpyridine.

2-Styryl-4-propyl-6-methylpyridine and its Salts.—2-Styryl-4-propyl-6-methylpyridine is an oily liquid possessing a characteristic pyridine like smell and could not be induced to crystallise and is soluble in common organic solvents.

The hydrochloride, obtained as sticky mass by passing dry hydrogen chloride into an ether solution of the base, crystallised from chloroform in long thin needles, m.p. 185°. It is soluble in chloroform, ethanol, acetone and water. (Found in dried material : N, 5.2; Cl, 12.5. $C_{17}H_{19}N$. HCl requires N, 5.1; Cl, 12.9 per cent). The hydrochloride on titration with bromine (1 mol.) in chloroform solution under ice-cooling gave a powder which crystallised from benzene in prisms, m.p. 168°.

The picrate, prepared from the base in ether or from the hydrochloride in acetone as a light yellow mass of needles, was recrystallised from chloroform, m.p. 225°. It is soluble in chloroform. [Found in material dried at 100° : C, 59.8; H, 3.9; N, 12.2. $C_{17}H_{19}N$. $C_6H_2(NO_2)_3OH$ requires C, 59.6; H, 4.1; N, 12.1 per cent].

The aurichloride was obtained by mixing together aqueous solutions of gold chloride and the hydrochloride as an orange coloured powder which crystallised from chloroform in thick bunches of spindle-shaped needles softening at 150° and gradually melting at 160°. It is soluble in chloroform, acetone and ethyl acetate. (Found in material dried at 100° : Au, 35.4. $C_{17}H_{19}N$. HCl. $AuCl_3$ requires Au, 35.4 per cent).

The chloroplatinate, prepared from the hydrochloride in aqueous solution as an amorphous powder, was crystallised from acetone in colourless prisms insoluble in chloroform and ethanol, m.p. 212°. On drying *in vacuo* at 100° it suffered no loss in weight. [Found in dried material : Pt, 22.1. $(C_{17}H_{19}N \cdot HCl)_2$. $PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 22.1 per cent].

The methiodide did not separate at room temperature but on warming chloroform solution of the base (1 g.) and methyl iodide (1 g.) at 70° for 2 hours a yellow powder (0.15 g.) was obtained which crystallised from chloroform-ether solution as short needles, m.p. 182-85° and unreacted base (0.75 g.) was recovered from the filtrate.

2 : 6-Distyryl-4-propylpyridine and its Salts. 2 : 6-Distyryl-4-propylpyridine.—The base from (B) was not sufficient for crystallisation and the solution in ether or chloroform showed a violet fluorescence.

The hydrochloride, prepared from the base, was crystallised from chloroform in needles, m.p. 225° and is soluble in chloroform, ethanol, methanol and acetone. (Found in material dried at 100° : N, 5.3; Cl, 10.0. $C_{24}H_{23}N$. HCl requires N, 5.9; Cl, 9.8 per cent).

The aurichloride, prepared by adding gold chloride to a solution of the hydrochloride in alcohol as an orange coloured powder, crystallised from acetone in stout spindle-

shaped needles, m.p. 190°. It is soluble in acetone and chloroform. Alcohol solution showed violet fluorescence. (Found in material dried at 100°: Au, 27.8. $C_{24}H_{23}N$. HCl. $AuCl_3$ requires Au, 29.6. $C_{24}H_{23}N$. HCl. $AuCl_3$. HCl requires Au, 28.0 per cent).

The chloroplatinate, prepared by adding an aqueous solution of platinic chloride to a solution of the hydrochloride in alcohol, was obtained as a powder, m.p. 246-48° (decomp.). It is soluble in alcohol and water. (Found in material dried at 100°: Pt, 28.4. $(C_{24}H_{23}N.HCl)_2$. $PtCl_4$ requires Pt, 28.4 per cent].

The picrate, prepared in ether solution, was crystallised from alcohol in yellow prisms, m.p. 215°. It is soluble in methanol and ethyl acetate. [Found in material dried at 100°: N, 10.3. $C_{24}H_{23}N$. $C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires N, 10.0 per cent].

Oxidation of 2-Styryl-4-propyl-6-methylpyridine: Formation of 4-Propyl-6-methylpyridine-2-carboxylic Acid.—An ice-cold solution of 2-styryl-4-propyl-6-methylpyridine (1 mol., 8.6 g) in acetone (500 c.c.) was oxidised with finely powdered potassium permanganate (2 mols., 18.1 g.) added in portions during an interval of half an hour. The reaction mixture was filtered and the mud after washing with acetone was extracted with hot water. The slightly yellow aqueous filtrate, when acidified with hydrochloric acid, gave benzoic acid (2 g.). The filtrate was treated with copper carbonate (4.5 g.) when a greenish copper salt (2 g.), which crystallised from alcohol in clusters of needles, m.p. 185-87°, was obtained. The filtrate gave no further yield of this salt. The copper salt was suspended in water and decomposed with hydrogen sulphide. The clear filtrate on evaporation to dryness in *vacuo* gave brownish residue (1 g.) which crystallised from ether in colourless needles, m.p. 60°.

The ammonium salt was obtained as a sticky brownish mass on passing ammonia into an ethereal solution of the acid.

The silver salt was prepared by mixing aqueous solutions of silver nitrate and the ammonium salt. It is a white powder, m.p. 222° (charring). It is soluble in alcohol and chloroform.

Decarboxylation of 4-propyl-6-methylpyridine-2-(a)-carboxylic Acid.—The acid (0.7 g.) was heated on a free flame with a trace of freshly precipitated copper powder for a few minutes when the base distilled with evolution of carbon dioxide.

2-Methyl-4-propylpyridine Picrate.—The base was converted into the picrate as bright yellow plates, m.p. 117°. It is soluble in chloroform, acetone, benzene and alcohol. (Found in material dried at 100°: C, 49.8; H, 4.5; N, 15.4. $C_9H_{13}N$. $C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 49.6; H, 4.4; N, 15.4 per cent).

The analyses were done by macro and micro methods.